

APPENDIX 2 - STUDENT PROFILE QUESTIONNAIRE

STUDENT PROFILE QUESTIONNAIRE

1) In which of the following courses are you currently enrolled?

- Bachelor's Degree in Computer Science
- Bachelor's Degree in Software Engineering
- Bachelor's Degree in Computer Engineering
- Bachelor's Degree in Information Systems
- Bachelor's Degree in Artificial Intelligence
- Other _____

2) What is your level of education?

- up to 4 semesters
- 5 to 8 semesters
- 9 to 12 semesters
- more than 12 semesters

3) Disregarding the course you are currently attending, please list the names of the undergraduate courses you have completed or not completed.

4) Do you currently work or have you ever worked in a professional activity (including internships) whose tasks are related to Computing?

- Yes
- No

5) Which of the following functions do you currently work or have you worked in professionally?

- Requirements Engineer/Analyst
- Business Analyst
- Designer
- Software Project Manager
- Programmer
- Tester
- Consultant
- Other

6) Have you ever performed the activity of software requirements elicitation?

- Yes, with guidance, in academic projects
- Yes, with guidance, in professional activities
- Yes, without guidance, in academic projects
- Yes, without guidance, in professional activities
- No

7) Have you ever prepared a software requirements specification document?

- Yes, with guidance, in academic projects
- Yes, with guidance, in professional activities
- Yes, without guidance, in academic projects
- Yes, without guidance, in professional activities
- No

8) How would you rate your general knowledge of Requirements Engineering?

- None
- I have little knowledge of the subject
- I can apply it in practice, but with guidance from someone
- I can apply it in practice, without guidance
- I have considerable theoretical and practical knowledge of the subject

9) How would you rate your general knowledge of LGPD (Brazilian General Data Protection Law)?

- None
- I have little knowledge of the subject
- I can apply it in practice, but with someone's guidance
- I can apply it in practice, without guidance
- I have considerable theoretical and practical knowledge of the subject